

Smartphone

Catalog for sustainability principles & action points

Sources can be viewed via QR code:

Guiding principles for sustainability – Smartphone

Guiding principles of sustainability are principles of action and behaviour for a product design that integrates sustainability into the product.

The guiding principles and their action points were developed from the sources mentioned in the footnote¹. The action points show which activities can be implemented in terms of sustainable product design.

Reusability

The term reuse indicates that already existing resources are used to create something new². In terms of the sustainability of IT (software & hardware), this can be applied to the reuse of software, libraries or components as well as the longest possible and most efficient use of hardware and software. Possible action points for the guiding principle of reusability are listed below:

- **Using sustainable materials:** Instead of using environmentally harmful materials such as plastic, companies can use materials such as paper, cardboard or carbon fibre that are better for the environment.
- **Fair working conditions along the supply chain:** Companies should ensure that all workers along the supply chain work under fair conditions by complying with guidelines and standards.
- **Reusing natural resources:** e.g. water can be reused for production through treatment which reduces the consumption of natural resources.
- **Multi-year warranty for products:** Companies can manufacture products that have a long warranty, which means that they are intended to work for several years.
- **Introduction of a circular economy:** For this, companies should ensure that products can be recycled or reused at the end of their life cycle instead of simply being thrown away.
- **Recycling** of basic materials or components for production
- **Conscious sourcing of materials:** Companies should ensure that they source materials such as rare earths under fair conditions without sourcing them from conflict regions.
- **Usage of sustainable packaging materials:** Instead of using plastic, companies should use environmentally friendly and reusable packaging.
- **Repairability of products:** Products should be designed in a way that allows repairing them easily, for example through **modular design** and replaceable components.
- **Ensuring battery longevity and replaceability:** Companies should ensure that batteries are easily replaceable and have a long duration.
- **Material coding of plastics:** This makes it easier to recycle products at the end of their service life.

¹ see Environment | Ethical consumer, 2023; Sustainability - Positive Marks | Ethical consumer, 2021; Hilty et al, 2017; Jardim, 2017; TCO Certification, 2023.

² Stützele, 2002, p.11.

- **Reconditioning of devices and components:** Companies can refurbish appliances and components so that their individual parts can be reused.
- **Avoidance of high repair costs:** The use of standardized parts and access to repair manuals can reduce repair costs.
- Use of standardized parts to ensure easy repairability
- **Free take-back of appliances when buying new ones:** Companies can offer a take-back program in which old appliances are taken back free of charge when customers buy new ones.
- **Passing on devices to family and friends or resellers:** Instead of throwing away old devices, they can be passed on to family members, friends or resellers to continue using them.

Avoiding negative effects

The production or consumption of certain goods as well as the provision and receipt of services can result in disadvantages (negative effects) for third parties. These effects have a negative impact on people and the environment but are not factored into the prices and profits of the producing or service-providing companies³. In terms of sustainability of IT (software & hardware), the aim is to avoid possible negative effects, such as the consumption of water for data centers instead of for agriculture⁴. Other negative effects are the need to handle toxic substances, conflicts due to rare earths⁵ and planned obsolescence⁶ (practice of designing products to break quickly or become obsolete in the short to mid-term⁷). Possible action points for avoiding or reversing the negative effects of IT are listed below:

- **Avoiding the use of materials from conflict areas,** e.g. rare earths
- Introducing a **circular economy:** manufacturing products in a way that allows reusing their components or design them with reused materials
- **Avoiding "green-washing":** Companies should not pretend to be environmentally friendly if they are not actually.
- **Avoidance of electricity from non-sustainable sources,** e.g. coal
- **Proactive climate policy:** e.g. through realistic targets, monitoring and audits of supply partners, using resource-efficient processes and technology and transparent reporting
- **Paying attention to water use:** Observing water withdrawal permits and paying attention to water consumption during production and use, e.g. through modern water management
- **Paying attention to land use:** e.g. through regular external audits and expert opinions
- **Avoiding toxic chemicals in products:** Products should not contain any hazardous chemicals. This can be ensured through special certifications.
- **Avoidance of non-clinical incinerators** (machines for burning waste): introducing product recycling and sustainable waste management.

³ See Waschbusch, 2018.

⁴ Benoit, 2023.

⁵ deutschlandfunk.de, undated.

⁶ Dallmus, 2022.

⁷ see iberdrola 2024.

- **Avoiding ozone-depleting chemicals** e.g. by switching to environmentally friendly alternatives
- **Preventing the release of toxic substances:** Special filters prevent toxic substances from being released into the environment.
- **Avoiding planned obsolescence:** designing products so that they do not intentionally break quickly
- **Transparency regarding negative effects:** reporting openly on the negative effects of their products and how they intend to deal with them
- **Establishing fairness & security along the supply chain,** e.g. through a compliance system, audits or regular external reviews
- **Anti-corruption measures:** establishing clear rules to prevent corruption
- **Avoiding electronic waste,** e.g. by increasing the useful life of devices
- **Controlling over sustainable usage behaviour,** e.g. through incentives and information
- **Conservation of habitats and resources,** e.g. through environmentally friendly production processes
- **Fair trade:** Trading fairly and ensuring fair and ethical business practices
- **Aiming for an environmental management system,** e.g. to identify and control environmental impacts
- **Aiming for an energy management system,** e.g. to optimize energy consumption
- **Evaluating CO2 footprint:** evaluating the CO2 emissions of products and defining measures to reduce them

Conversation of resources

Conversation of resources refers to the efficient use of natural resources to minimize their consumption and preserve their availability for present and future generations. This approach aims to reduce environmental impact, avoid waste and promote sustainable production and consumption habits. Conversation of resources is based on the principle that natural resources are limited and should be used responsibly to minimize environmental impacts and maintain ecological balances⁸. Possible action points for this guiding principle are listed below:

- **Introduction of an energy-saving mode** as standard for hardware and software, e.g. by automatically activating sleep mode
- **Recycling of components:** Defining processes for the recovery of valuable materials
- Aiming for component **longevity** by developing new components
- **Using reusable materials,** e.g. recycled materials and modular components
- **Interchangeable components,** e.g. thanks to a modular design
- **Avoidance of planned obsolescence,** e.g. through designs that enable repair
- **Using sustainable or environmentally friendly materials,** e.g. bio-based plastics
- **Reducing the consumption of natural resources** such as water, energy, etc. in production, e.g. by tracking and optimizing resources along the supply chain, adhering to ethical manufacturing practices
- **Certifications:** Products should have labels that show that they comply with environmental standards.

⁸ see Haufe, 2021.

- **A++ energy label to** demonstrate the energy efficiency of the technology
- **Energy-saving IT**, e.g. through optimized algorithms or energy-saving hardware
- Aiming for a **long product service life**
- **Sustainable packaging material** e.g. recyclable cardboard boxes or bioplastics
- **Repairability**, e.g. via a modular design
- **Controlling over sustainable usage behaviour**, e.g. via sustainability settings on the product, including energy-saving mode, etc.
- **Conservation of habitats and resources**, e.g. through environmentally friendly production processes
- **Aiming for an environmental management system**, e.g. to identify and control environmental impacts
- **Aiming for an energy management system**, e.g. to optimize energy consumption
- **Evaluating the CO2 footprint**: You should be able to evaluate the CO2 emissions of the products and take measures to reduce them.
- **Monitoring working conditions along the supply chain**, e.g. through regular audits and inspections
- **Usage of data-based analyses** to improve resource efficiency and reduce waste
- Use few components: usage-based device design

Minimisation of data transmission

Data transmission combines methods for passing on information from an information source (transmitter) to an information sink (receiver). This can be transported by electrical, optical signals or electromagnetic waves⁹. The transmission of data has an impact on our environment, for instance through land use and water consumption of data centers. For this reason, a minimal use of data transmission is a further means of achieving sustainability in IT (software). Possible action points for the guiding principle of economic data transmission are listed below:

- **Energy efficiency**, e.g. through the use of renewable energies
- Restricting the transfer of user data, e.g. by the operating system to the manufacturer
- Adapting the required **computing power** to the usage
- Avoiding **health effects**, such as loss of vision, through clever design or a suitable screen
- Adapting **user experience (UX)** to the group of users

Health and accessibility

Health and accessibility of IT in terms of sustainability can be defined as follows. Health is about designing IT in a way that does not cause **physical and mental harm to health**. Ideally, technology is designed in a way so that it counteracts unhealthy usage patterns and actively supports users in promoting a healthy lifestyle¹⁰ e.g. by **avoiding suggestive notifications**. Accessibility refers to how easy the IT is accessible and useable. High accessibility means

⁹ data transmission, n.d.

¹⁰ Grosch et al., 2023.

that access to data and software is network-based and **inexpensive** or reasonably priced. In addition, the diverse population should be taken into account e.g. through **accessibility**, which can be expressed in an audio function of websites for the deaf or simple language for people with disabilities.¹¹ The following are possible action points for this guiding principle:

- Observing **ergonomics**, e.g. by designing the device (e.g. size, width, material), screens and input devices (e.g. mouse, keyboard, etc.)
- Creating accessibility, e.g. through simple language, image descriptions and audio functions as well as adjustable contrasts. Raising awareness, e.g. by providing users with information about healthy IT practices
- Ensuring **data protection**, e.g. through secure and private ways of storing data
- Promoting **sleep hygiene**, e.g. through notifications that inform about the negative impact of using IT devices shortly before falling asleep (sleep disorders)
- Reducing stress, e.g. through adjustable notification modes on IT devices
- **Health-promoting settings**, e.g. through displays with blue light or black and white filters
- Implementing options for break regulations, e.g. through automated reminders for breaks or short movement clips
- Consideration of **linguistic diversity**
- Disposing of hazardous materials at authorized collection points or recycling facilities to avoid health effects.

¹¹Grosch et al., 2023.